

Data steward Onboarding sheet

Welcome to the data steward network @ WUR! To help you get started and find more information, click on the buttons below.

Sign up, meet, and join!

Mailing list

Let us know you are a new data steward and get on the data steward mailing list to keep up-to-date

Viva Engage Group

Join and check out the data steward intranet-group

Join meetings

Meet up with the coordinating data steward of your Science group and join periodically data steward meetings

Course

Optional: Sign up for WUR research data management course/Essentials 4 data support course (external)

Role and tasks

Check out the tasks description and go through the list with your chair group holder/ business unit manager

DMPonline

Sign in with your institutional credentials and explore DMPonline to create data management plans

Privacy officer

Meet up with your Science group's Privacy officer

Security officer

Meet up with your Science group's Security officer

LCRDM mailinglist

Optional: Sign up for The National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM) mailinglist

Where to find information?

WUR research data policy

WUR Research Data Management website

Open Science @ WUR ambitions & themes

FAIR principles explained

FAIR self-assessment tool

Differences between Open Data, FAIR and Research Data Management explained

Find other data stewards at WUR

WUR Data Storage Finder

WUR Repository Finder